

CHEMICAL SCIENCES

STUDY OF ELECTROPHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF TBBISE₃ COMPOUND

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Abstract

As a result of the research, it was found that in the temperature range of 300÷500 K, an increase in the thermo-emf coefficient is observed and at ~510 K it reaches its maximum value. However, above ~570 K, the thermal emf coefficient of both compounds and alloys of Bi₂Se₃-Tb₂Se₃ solid solutions tends to decrease. It is known from the literature that such a temperature dependence of the thermo-emf coefficient is inherent in semiconductor materials with a complex band structure.

It has been established that the intrinsic conduction region begins approximately in the temperature range 450÷550 K.

Keywords: synthesis, alloy, semiconductor, temperature

The efficiency of production of new technology devices is inextricably linked with the development of semiconductor materials science [1-3]. At present, it is not always possible to meet the demands of semiconductor electronics with binary semiconductors, so an intensive search for complex materials with a favorable combination of properties is carried out. The solution to this problem is based on modern physical and chemical analysis and research into a complex of electro-physical parameters that allow us to identify the existence of various new phases in semiconductor systems, determine the methods and conditions of synthesis, as well as the growth of modern single crystals and their implementation in various sectors of the national economy.

Research and production of new semiconductor compounds of complex composition is one of the most pressing problems [4-6]. The study of two-component systems, the construction of state diagrams play a major role in obtaining ternary compounds. Investigation of the physical properties of these types of compounds

shows that they play a major role in semiconductor technology [7-9].

By studying the chemical interaction in the Bi₂Se₃-Tb₂Se₃ systems, state diagrams were constructed and congruent-melting new compounds with the composition TbBiSe₃ were found, T_{melt.Bi} = 1020 °K, respectively, lattice parameters a=11.62; b=11.824 c=4.11 Å.

To measure the physical properties, the compound was synthesized and the corresponding geometric forms were prepared. The main physical properties of TbBiSe₃ compounds are given in Table 1 at 300 °K. At the same time, the thermal conductivity of TbBiSe₃ is 14.2 W/cm·min.

For semiconductors, each of the three parameters is different, and this can be considered normal. From the graph of the dependence of electrical conductivity on temperature $\lg\sigma \sim f(103/T)$, the width of the forbidden band of the compounds (ΔE_t) is calculated. For TbBiSe₃ $\Delta E_t = 0.72$ eV. This compound has an electron type of conductivity..

Table 1

Physical properties of compounds TbBiSe₃

Composition	T _m . °C	Thermo emf α, mKv/deg	Electro conductivity δ, om ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹	Warm conductivity W/cm hail	Charge carrier mobility cm ² /in*cm	Inhibit Width zones	Conductivity type n, p
TbBiSe ₃	1020K 750°C	126	129	14,2	52,2	0,72	n

Temperature dependence of specific electrical conductivity and thermo-e.m.f. coefficient compounds TbBiSe₃ are shown in Figures 1. As can be seen from

the figures, starting from about 450÷550 K, it also indicates the onset of an intrinsic conduction region. The band gap values of the compounds were calculated

from the tangent of the angle of the graphs $\lg\sigma \sim f(103/T, K)$ in the intrinsic conduction region.

Figure 1 Temperature dependence of electrical conductivity and thermal e.m.f. coefficient of $TbBiSe_3$

In the temperature range of 300÷500 K, an increase in the thermal e.m.f. coefficient is observed and at ~510 K it reaches its maximum value. However, above ~570 K, the thermo-e.m.f. coefficient of the compounds tends to decrease. It is known from the literature that such a temperature dependence of the thermo-e.m.f. coefficient is inherent in semiconductor materials with a complex band structure. In the initial temperature range of the studied samples, the change in α with respect to temperature qualitatively agrees with the temperature dependence of the thermo-e.m.f. coefficient with certain theoretical calculations, according to the following formula and under the assumption $n = \text{const}$, m^k/m_0 (n is the concentration of current carriers, m^k/m_0 is the effective mass of current carriers).

$$\alpha = \pm \frac{k}{e} \left[\frac{\left(r + \frac{5}{2}\right) F_{\frac{5}{2}}(\mu^*)}{\left(r + \frac{3}{2}\right) F_0(\mu^*)} - \mu^* \right]$$

where, k is the Boltzmann constant, e is the electron charge, r is the scattering parameter of current carriers, $F_{\frac{5}{2}}(\mu^*)$ and $F_0(\mu^*)$ are the Fermi integrals, μ^* is the chemical potential, calculated and the dependence $\alpha_{\text{theor}} \sim f(T)$ is constructed.

The change in the thermo-e.m.f. coefficient above 560-570 K can be attributed to the law for semiconductors with a complex band structure;

$$\alpha = \frac{\alpha_1 \sigma_1 + \alpha_2 \sigma_2}{\sigma_1 + \sigma_2}$$

Here, α_1 , α_2 and σ_1 , σ_2 are the coefficients of thermal emf and electrical conductivity, due to the first and second subbands of the valence band (assuming that the valence band of the samples under study, similar to the band structure of pure Bi_2Se_3 , consists of two sub-

bands). However, the valence band may consist of several subbands, and in this case, carriers of the third type may participate in changes in the kinetic coefficients (for example, α and σ), which is why the change in the thermo-e.m.f. coefficient will be characterized as,

$$\alpha = \frac{\alpha_1 \sigma_1 + \alpha_2 \sigma_2 + \alpha_n \sigma_n}{\sigma_1 + \sigma_2 + \sigma_n}$$

where, α_n and σ_n are thermal emf and conductivity due to the appearance of carriers of a new (third) type. A smooth decrease in α at high temperatures indicates a similar picture that took place in Bi_2Se_3 . If the decrease in α at high temperatures had a sharp character, then this, in all likelihood, would be associated with the onset of an intrinsic conduction region or the approaching melting temperature of the samples.

The observed change in the thermoelectric coefficients and electrical conductivity leads to the achievement of favorable values of thermoelectric power ($\alpha\sigma$). However, for a more accurate determination of the thermoelectric efficiency of the alloy, the temperature dependences of the total thermal conductivity in the range of 300-850 K were also studied. It turned out that up to a temperature of ~700 K, the change in χ total occurs according to a negative power law. This indicates normal photonic processes occurring in Bi_2Se_3 compounds in the solid solution $(Tb_2Se_3)_{1-x}(Bi_2Se_3)_x$.

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